

susceptible Jaya. At 20-25 d after treatment, when BPH population peaked, adults and nymphs were counted on 10 randomly selected hills per treatment. BPH populations were larger in 1983 than in 1982.

Carbofuran, BPMC, and carbosulfan controlled BPH best (see table). *ℒ*

Mites attack IR56 in Vallanad, Tamil Nadu

M. Swamiappan, Entomology Department, Agricultural College, Tamil Nadu Agricultural University, Killikulam, Tirunelveli 627252, India

Rice mite *Oligonychus oryzae* (Hirst) attacked IR56 on the State Seed Farm in Vallanad in Sep 1985. The farm is irrigated for three seasons in a year. At 50 d after planting in a 6.5-ha block with 4 ha of IR50 and 2.5 ha of IR56, IR56 had 90-100% infestation and IR50 was mite-free.

IR56 had a mean population of 70 nymphs and adult mites/2 cm² leaf area and a mean of 96 eggs/cm² leaf area. Eggs, nymphs, and adults were on both leaf blade surfaces. Eggs were globular and pale white, nymphs were white, and adults were greyish white.

Mite feeding caused white spots on leaf surfaces, which later coalesced into white patches. Infested plants became yellowish white with severe leaf mottling.

Unusually high temperatures and dry weather (mean maximum temperature 35°C and minimum 30°C) for 30 d before the infestation may have encouraged high populations. *ℒ*

Rice gall midge (GM) in Tarai region of Uttar Pradesh

P. K. Pathak, Entomology Department, College of Agriculture, GBPUAT; B. R. Agrora, BASF, Pilibhit (U.P.); and M. N. Lal, Entomology Department, GBPUAT, Pantnagar 263145, U.P., India

The rice GM *Orseolia oryzae* is considered to be one of the major pests of rice. It has been reported in small pockets of Eastern Uttar Pradesh. In 1972, in the central and western Tarai region where rice is grown as a kharif crop, gall midge was reported from a very small area in Lakhimpur Kheri district. Since then, there was no report of its occurrence. While conducting a production oriented survey in 1984, we came across GM-infested fields in Mala

village and the Amaria block of Pilibhit district. Infestation was observed in the widely grown variety Jaya, which was then in the panicle initiation stage. There was 20-25% infestation in Mala, and 10-15% in the Amaria block.

Infested tillers were brought to the glasshouse to observe adult emergence. Only one female fly emerged and was identified as *Orseolia* sp. (presumably rice GM). Along with the adults, some parasites also emerged and were identified as *Propieroscytus mirificus* Girault (Pteromalidae). These may be larval, pupal, or larval-pupal parasites.

The infested fields were along the forest but areas one kilometer away from it showed no GM infestation. The same forest belt continues toward the western side, Pantnagar being about 40 km away from Mala village. The GM appears to spread toward the western side of Tarai along the forest at a slow rate. Although no widespread infestation has been reported in Tarai, the trend is alarming.

In Tarai region, the temperature goes down below 0°C during winter. The survival and perpetuation of GM during off season is worth investigating, particularly its behavior in biotype differential rice varieties. *ℒ*

Pest Control and Management WEEDS

Influence of different ecological situations on weed emergence in wetland rice

P.A. Joseph, Agricultural Research Station, Mannuthy, Kerala, India

Thirteen locations surveyed during the rabi season (Sep-Dec) of 1984 revealed the predominance of sedges in double-cropped wet rice fields in Trichur district. Eleven species of weeds

classified under five groups were identified as follows: *Echinochloa crus-galli* (grass); *Cyperus iria*, *C. difformis*, *Scirpus supinus*, and *Fimbristylis miliacea* (sedges); *Ludwigia octovalvis*,

Table 1. Effect of different ecological conditions on weed count.

Treatment	Weed count (no./m ²)										
	<i>Echinochloa crus-galli</i>	<i>Scirpus supinus</i>	<i>Cyperus iria</i>	<i>Cyperus difformis</i>	<i>Fimbristylis miliacea</i>	<i>Sphaeranthus indicus</i>	<i>Sphenoclea zeylanica</i>	<i>Ludwigia octovalvis</i>	<i>Nymphaea nouchali</i>	<i>Monochoria vaginalis</i>	<i>Marsilea quadrifolia</i>
Transplanted rice	2.4 (1.4)	98.0 (9.6)	0.0 (0.6)	2.4 (1.4)	0.0 (0.6)	0.8 (0.9)	9.8 (2.9)	1.2 (1.1)	3.2 (1.5)	18.4 (4.0)	2.2 (1.4)
Wet sown rice	0.0 (0.6)	56.8 (7.2)	10.0 (3.2)	67.2 (7.6)	6.4 (2.3)	0.0 (0.6)	2.4 (1.4)	0.0 (0.6)	0.0 (0.6)	14.4 (3.7)	0.0 (0.6)
Wet fallow	2.4 (1.4)	267.2 (16.3)	6.4 (2.5)	10.6 (3.2)	0.0 (0.6)	0.0 (0.6)	6.6 (2.5)	4.2 (2.0)	1.6 (1.1)	8.8 (2.5)	1.2 (1.1)
Dry fallow	0.2 (0.7)	273.6 (16.4)	8.2 (2.9)	24.2 (4.8)	149.2 (11.7)	24.8 (4.9)	0.0 (0.6)	0.0 (0.6)	0.0 (0.6)	0.0 (0.6)	0.0 (0.6)
CD at 5%	ns	3.4	0.7	3.0	2.8	1.0	1.2	0.8	ns	2.3	0.7

^aFigures in parentheses are converted values.